

The Decomposition of Potassium Mangani-oxalate in Plane Polarised, Circularly Polarised and Ordinary Light.

By

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Christiansen (*Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 27, 325) describes a method for the preparation of crystals of pure manganic acetate and observes that when manganic acetate is dissolved in a concentrated solution of potassium oxalate a solution of deep red colour is obtained due to the formation of potassium mangani-oxalate. He was also able to obtain crystals of this salt, but they decomposed in the dark and very rapidly in light.

Werner found that potassium cobalti-oxalate, as generally prepared, is a racemic mixture and he succeeded in resolving it into its optically active varieties. Potassium mangani-oxalate must also, according to Werner's theory, be a racemic mixture of asymmetric molecules. In some previous investigations in this laboratory the influence of the state of polarisation of light on the velocity of photochemical reactions resulting in the formation of asymmetric molecules has been studied. (Ghosh and Purkayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 261). In this reaction, however, it is the asymmetric molecules which undergo decomposition under the influence of light into inactive components. It has been observed that the velocity of decomposition for the same intensity of plane polarised and ordinary light is almost the same; circularly polarised light appears to be a little more effective, but this statement cannot be made with

confidence as the temperature of the reaction chamber could only be kept constant within $\pm 0.2^{\circ}\text{C}$ when working at 6°C . This reaction is an ideal one for the application of Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence, in that a molecule by absorption of light disintegrates of itself without any side reaction and it has been found that under favourable conditions, one quantum actually transforms one molecule.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The room temperature at Dacca varies from 25° to 33° and at these temperatures the velocity of decomposition of potassium mangani-oxalate in the dark was found to be very large; in fact it very largely masks the effect of light on the velocity of this decomposition. The decomposition in the dark was found to have a large temperature coefficient and it was felt that if photochemical reaction could be carried out at low temperatures the effect of the dark reaction would be comparatively small. The problem is to allow a parallel beam of light to enter a glass reaction vessel, maintained at a low temperature, without undergoing distortion or considerable loss in intensity. It is therefore necessary to avoid completely the deposition of dew on the glass windows of the low temperature enclosure in which the reaction vessel is kept. This is a difficult affair in a moist tropical country. After various unsuccessful devices were attempted, the following experimental arrangement gave satisfactory results.

A small water-tight brass box covered with ebonite sheets on the exterior, with glass windows on four sides and with a close fitting sliding top made also of ebonite contained the stoppered reaction vessel (1.65 cm. cube). Cold clear water from a thermostat maintained at the

FIG. 1.

desired low temperature was made to flow through this box by means of a circulating pump run by a hot air motor. This ebonite covered box was then placed inside a larger box of copper fitted with glass windows on four sides, through which distilled water at room temperature was circulated very rapidly (Fig. 1). The cold glass windows of the inner ebonite covered box are thus always in contact on the outside with distilled water at room temperature, and the light in entering these windows does not suffer any scattering. The larger copper box is so fixed on the stage of a König-Martens spectrophotometer that one of the two parallel pencils into which the light from the source is split up, passes through the reaction vessel placed inside the ebonite covered box and the other pencil passes only through the cold water circulating in the box. The experimental arrangement is in other respects analogous to that used in the investigation of the photobromination of stilbene and of cinnamic acid in this laboratory (Ghosh and Purkayastha, *loc. cit.*). Only in this instance a 500 c. p. pointolite lamp was used. A thermometer passing through a hole on the ebonite box indicated the temperature of the reaction vessel. Its temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.2^\circ$ during the experiment while working at 6°C and within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ at higher temperatures.

A solution of potassium mangani-oxalate at the desired temperature was obtained by dissolving a weighed quantity of manganic acetate in a given volume of potassium oxalate solution of known strength previously cooled to the temperature of the cold water in the thermostat. The reaction vessel was quickly filled with the cold solution of potassium mangani-oxalate, stoppered and placed inside the box. The circulating pump was started and the screen cutting off the light from the pointolite lamp removed.

Molecular Extinction Coefficients of Potassium Mangani-Oxalate in various Regions of the Spectrum.

Potassium mangani-oxalate in solution is coloured pinkish red and has been found to have absorption in all the regions of the spectrum. The extinction coefficients were measured by the rotation of the angle in the König-Martén spectrophotometer and calculated from the equation,

$$\epsilon = \frac{\log_{10} \tan \alpha_1 - \log_{10} \tan \alpha_2}{ct}$$

The values were obtained by examining an M/800 solution. The absorption being very great in all regions excepting red, orange and yellow, more concentrated solutions could not be employed. The results are given in Table I and are plotted in Fig. 2.

TABLE I.

Wave-length.	ϵ	$\log \epsilon$
6563	32.25	1.5086
6110	43.10	1.6345
5790	90.00	1.9542
5461	178.0	2.2504
5015	254.0	2.4048
4861	266.7	2.4260
4471	151.7	2.1810

Table II gives the values for $\log_{10} \tan \alpha_1 - \log_{10} \tan \alpha_2$ for various concentrations of potassium mangani-oxalate at wave-length $579\mu\mu$. In this region of the spectrum Beer's law is obeyed as will be at once obvious from Fig. 3 where the curve giving the values of $\log_{10} \tan \alpha_1 - \log_{10} \tan \alpha_2$, plotted against concentration, is found to be a

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

straight line. Readings to test Beer's law in regions of shorter wave-length could not be taken owing to very great absorption. It is clear that from the readings in the spectrophotometer for the above wave-length the concentrations can conversely be calculated.

TABLE II.

Concentration.	$\text{Log}_{10} \tan \alpha_1 - \log_{10} \tan \alpha_2.$
$50 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$	1.4254
$40 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$	1.5498
$25 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$	1.7035
$12.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{M}$	1.8657

Velocity Measurements at 6°C.

Even at 6°, the temperature at which the experiments were carried out, potassium mangani-oxalate decomposes pretty rapidly in the dark and the rate of this reaction was first measured. Table III gives the results of this measurement, k being the velocity constant of mono-molecular reaction.

TABLE III.

Time in minutes.	Conc. $\times 10^4$	k
0	43.25	...
30	37.25	0.004988
60	32.00	0.005014
90	27.25	0.005129
120	23.25	0.005152
		Mean 0.005065

Reaction in Dark at 16°.

TABLE IV.

Time in minutes.	Conc. $\times 10^4$	k
0	49.00	...
20	39.00	0.011386
40	31.50	0.011017
60	26.00	0.010580
80	20.75	0.010143
100	16.50	0.010679
		Mean 0.010800

Reaction in Ordinary White Light at 6° and 16°.

Intensity of incident energy = 19800 ergs per sq. cm. per sec. as measured by a Johansen thermopile and galvanometer calibrated with a Hefner lamp.

TABLE V.

Temperature 6°.

Time in minutes.	Conc. $\times 10^4$ mols.	k
0	43.25	...
10	35.00	0.02114
20	28.75	0.02038
30	23.25	0.02065
40	19.00	0.02054
		Mean 0.02068

TABLE VI.
Temperature 16°.

Time in minutes.	Conc. × 10 ⁴ mols	k
0	43.50	...
5	37.25	0.03109
10	32.00	0.03068
15	27.00	0.03174
20	23.25	0.03128
25	20.00	0.03105
		Mean 0.03115

It will be seen from Tables III and V that at 6° the velocity of reaction in light is exactly about four times the velocity in dark.

Effect due to Light only.

k in light — k in dark = $0.02068 - 0.00506 = 0.01562$ at 6°; or = $0.03115 - 0.01080 = 0.02035$ at 16°.

Temperature coefficient between 6° and 16° of velocity of reaction in light = $\frac{0.02035}{0.01562} = 1.30$.

Temperature coefficient of velocity of reaction in dark

$$= \frac{0.01080}{0.00506} = 2.13.$$

It was found that the concentration of potassium oxalate when varied between N and $N/10$ had no perceptible influence on the velocity of the decomposition.

Reaction in Plane and Circularly Polarised Lights.

Intensities of light in these three cases were adjusted by using lenses of suitable foci, so that they were almost equal to one another and equal to that of ordinary white light employed in the experiments above.

TABLE VII.

Temperature 6°.

Intensity.	Kind of light.	k
19800 ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.	Ordinary	0.02068
19620 " " "	Plain polarised	0.02038
20070 " " "	Circularly polarised.	0.02254

It will be seen from the above table that the velocity of photo-decomposition in ordinary and plane polarised white light is the same, but circularly polarised light has a slightly greater efficiency.

Effect of Adding Oxalic Acid to the Reaction Mixture on the Velocity of Decomposition.

Two series of measurements were made by adding 0.2 g. and 2.0 g. of oxalic acid to a litre of normal potassium oxalate solution. The following table gives the results obtained at 6° in darkness and in light.

TABLE VIII.

0.2 g. of oxalic acid per litre.

Intensity.	Kind of light.	k
...	In darkness	0.004577
19800 ergs per sq. cm. sec ⁻¹ .	Ordinary light	0.020079
19620 " "	Plane polarised light	0.020930
20070 " "	Circularly polarised light	0.023437

TABLE VIII—Continued.

2.0 g. of oxalic acid per litre.

...	In darkness	0.002588
19800 ergs per sq. cm. sec ⁻¹	Ordinary light	0.015249
19620 " "	Plane polarised light	0.015856
20070 " "	Circularly polarised light	0.018774

The effect of adding oxalic acid is thus to depress the velocity of decomposition both in darkness and in light. Otherwise the results are similar to those obtained in neutral potassium oxalate solution.

Temperature Coefficient of Velocity of Decomposition in Darkness and in Light.

TABLE IX.

0.2 g. of oxalic acid per litre.

Temp.	Velocity constant	Temp. coeff. per 10°
6°	In darkness—0.004577	2.06
16°	In darkness—0.009562	
6°	In light—0.02007	1.5
16°	In light—0.02974	
6°	(k in light—k in dark)=0.01560	
16°	(k in light—k in dark)=0.02028	

TABLE IX.—*Continued.**2 g. of oxalic acid per litre.*

Temp.	Velocity constant.	Temp. coeff. per 10°
6°	In darkness -0.003588	3.16
16°	In darkness -0.01136	
26°	In darkness -0.03767	
6°	In light -0.01242	3.30
16°	In light -0.02341	
26°	In light -0.05748	
6°	(k in light $-k$ in dark) -0.00883	1.36
16°	(k in light $-k$ in dark) -0.01205	
26°	(k in light $-k$ in dark) -0.01979	

The temperature coefficient for the dark reaction in all these cases is very large ranging from 2.06 in neutral oxalate solution to 3.30 in oxalate solution containing 2.0 g. of oxalic acid per litre. The temperature coefficient for the velocity of photochemical decomposition on the other hand is quite small, near about 1.3. This is in conformity with other experimental data in this field and is to be expected.

Influence of Intensity of Incident Light on the Velocity of Photochemical Decomposition.

M/200 of manganic acetate dissolved in *N*-potassium oxalate containing 2 g. of oxalic acid per litre was used in the three following experiments.

TABLE X

Intensity of light.	k in light.	(k in light - k in dark)
16100 ergs.cm ² sec ⁻¹	0.01242	0.00883
19800 " "	0.01525	0.01166
24300 " "	0.02040	0.01681

The velocity as is to be expected increases with increase in the intensity of the incident light but there is no simple relation between the velocity constant and the intensity of *incident* radiation. In order, however, to determine the relation between the quantity of chemical transformation and the energy of the light, the quantity of light absorbed must be measured and this measurement is described in the next section.

Velocity of Photochemical Decomposition in approximately Monochromatic Light of Wave-length 488 $\mu\mu$.

To obtain an approximately monochromatic radiation of wave-length 488 $\mu\mu$ Plotnikow (*Photochemische Versuchstechnik*, p. 59) recommends the use of two filters, one a solution of Doppelgrün SF (0.02%) and another of CuSO₄·5H₂O (15%) each of a thickness of 20 mm. to be used together. These filters were employed with white light in the following experiments (M/200 manganic acetate dissolved in neutral *N*-potassium oxalate solution was used).

TABLE XI.

*Intensity of blue light 6075 ergs per cm² per sec.
Temperature 6°.*

Time in minutes.	Conc. $\times 10^4$	Velocity constant.
0	48.2	...
10	39.00	0.02114
20	31.75	0.02003
30	28.00	0.01808
40	24.00	0.01741
50	20.50	0.01707
60	17.20	0.01714

TABLE XII.

*Intensity of blue light 2295 ergs per cm² per sec.
Temperature 6°.*

Time in minutes.	Conc. $\times 10^4$	Velocity constant.
0	47.75	...
10	43.25	0.00989
20	39.25	0.00980
30	36.00	0.00941
45	32.50	0.00855
60	29.50	0.00803
75	26.50	0.00784

The velocity of decomposition in dark is 0.005083. It will be noticed from Tables XI and XII that the velocity of decomposition in blue light is roughly proportional to the intensity of incident radiation; but the velocity constants fall as decomposition progresses.

Polarised Light.

Experiments carried on in plane polarised and circularly polarised light with the colour filters used in the above two experiments and with an incident of radiation = 6075 ergs per sq. cm. per sec. gave almost identical results with those given in Table XI.

Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical Equivalence.

This law is strictly applicable to monochromatic radiation. In the present investigation the reaction for obvious experimental difficulties could not be carried on in monochromatic light, but the use of filters mentioned above gave a beam which approximated in quality to monochromatic radiation.

From the first two readings in Table XI we find that 9.2×10^{-4} gm. mols are decomposed in 600 seconds, per litre. Therefore the actual number of molecules decomposed per c.c. per sec.

$$= \frac{9.2 \times 10^{-7} \times 6.1 \times 10^{23}}{600} = 9.3 \times 10^{14}.$$

The number of molecules decomposed per sq. cm. of the surface under the influence of radiation in the reaction cell = $9.3 \times 10^{14} \times 1.65$ (1.65 being the thickness of the reaction cell). Of these 1/4th the number of molecules are decomposed by thermal energy alone, so that the number of molecules decomposed photochemically

$$= \frac{9.3 \times 10^{14} \times 1.65 \times 3}{4} = 11.5 \times 10^{14} \text{ mol.}$$

It was found that with the light source and experimental arrangement used, the intensity of the transmitted blue light through the reaction cell filled with only potassium oxalate solution was equal to $5175 \text{ ergs cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ while the intensity of the beam with the cell filled with

potassium oxalate solution in which manganic acetate was dissolved (concentration of the manganic salt being equal to $45 \times 10^{-4}M$, about the average concentration between 48 and $39 \times 10^{-4}M$) was equal to 1575 ergs per sq. cm. per sec. The energy absorbed in passing through the thickness of solution in the cell per sq. cm. per sec. is therefore the difference of these quantities *viz.*, $5175 - 1575 = 3600$ ergs $cm^{-2} sec^{-1}$. One quantum of blue light

$$= \frac{hc}{\lambda} = \frac{6.55 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}}{488 \times 10^{-7}}$$

The number of quanta of light absorbed by the decomposing substance is therefore equal to

$$\frac{3600 \times 488 \times 10^{-7}}{6.55 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}} = 8.94 \times 10^{14}$$

Therefore the number of molecules decomposed per quantum of energy absorbed

$$= \frac{11.5 \times 10^{14}}{8.94 \times 10^{14}} = 1.28$$

or roughly one quantum transforms one molecule. It is clear therefore that in this case the law of Einstein is quite applicable. The fact that the temperature coefficient of the velocity of photochemical decomposition is just a little above unity lends additional support to this conclusion.

Our thanks are due to Mr. Sailendra Nath Sen who carried out a large number of preliminary experiments in this connection.